

PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF IMPROVING MEDIA LITERACY IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the concept of media literacy and the reasons for its emergence are explored as a pedagogical problem of increasing media literacy in the higher education system. In addition, the concepts of information, media, digital communication and media were particularly touched upon.

Key words: media, literacy, media literacy, information, Internet, digital communication, digital technologies, credit module.

In order for a person to live safely in a certain ecological environment, he must first be aware of the characteristics of living in that environment. Similarly, in order for a modern person to live safely in the media environment in which he spends most of his time and lives, it is also important for him to be aware of the characteristics of the environment in which he himself is active and which influences his decision-making. In recent years, the development of information technologies, in particular, the emergence of the Internet, has, firstly, increased the speed of information preparation and transmission several times, and secondly, expanded the possibilities of receiving it to an unprecedented extent. Therefore, in this process, the accuracy or incorrectness of the information being transmitted is not taken into account to a great extent. As a result, the purpose and purpose behind information are being distorted, and it is being used for various purposes and interests. This, in turn, has had an impact on educational processes. One of the pressing problems of today is that these influences do not negatively affect students of educational institutions, in particular higher education institutions, as an ideological threat. In this case, media literacy is important for society, especially for young people. This means, first of all, the importance of owning information, evaluating it and using it in compliance with ethical rules. So, what is media literacy? First, let's talk about the concept of literacy.

The simplest definition of media literacy is: the ability to access, analyze, evaluate, create, and act on information using various forms of media. Simply put, media literacy builds on the foundations of traditional literacy and offers new forms of reading and writing. Media literacy enables people to be critical and creative thinkers, effective communicators, and active citizens.

Media literacy serves to form the skills to sort through everyday information transmitted and received through the media, to make the right decisions in any situation after receiving various information, to understand where the information comes from, by whom, and for what purpose, and whose interests it reflects.

In our opinion, media literacy, together with the above ideas, is a critical view of all information transmitted through the media, an impartial approach to them, and a conscious approach to sorting each transmitted information.

The goal of media literacy is to develop the skills to sort the information distributed by them and accept what is necessary, while understanding the priorities and shortcomings of each media, its main task is to understand the manipulative power of any information consumed by people and to limit it. It is also to help people understand the role of the media (media) and citizen journalism.

Media literacy is an integral part of media education. At the same time, its manifestations are increasing. Today, the concept of media literacy is used in conjunction with the concept of media education in the reception, selection, analysis, and evaluation of media information. Media education [2, 3]:

- the study of media in an integrated, interdisciplinary manner in the curriculum;
- the analysis of the “media topic” within a specific discipline;
- a critical approach to the media through practical work and analysis;
- the study of its form, technologies, and methods of information transmission;
- the study of media agencies, their social, political, and cultural role;
- the student’s work with the media;
- research activities;
- studies the impact of the media on the audience through language and art.

Today, along with media literacy and media education, digital technologies are developing rapidly in the education sector. In this era, when the speed of information acquisition and use has increased significantly, the use of digital technologies in the education system is of great importance in improving the quality of education and educating socially active youth. Previously, we used to conduct educational programs in the traditional way, that is, lectures through large-sized books and manuals. This, in turn, did not ensure that the quality of education was so high. Currently, the process of digitization of education has begun to improve the quality of education. When education is provided through

digital technologies, the methods of education become easier for students. In this, multimedia, overhead projectors, computers, laptops, Internet-connected televisions, telephone lines, smart boards, and projectors play the role of the educational system. Conducting classes with such tools for teachers ensures that the quality of education is improved.

The educational process in higher education institutions (HEMIS) is a complex process that includes many aspects, such as organizational, management, and development of cognitive activity in the preparation of highly qualified specialists. In order to prevent the above situations (eliminating excessive paperwork, processes related to the spending of professors and teachers' time on filling out internal documents), today all HEMIS in our republic have been transferred to the credit-module system of education. In turn, working in this system requires media literacy from both professors and students.

The credit education system involves planning the educational activities of professors and teachers and students in the personal educational trajectory for the current academic year. The basis of any educational process is the student's personal educational plan, which is drawn up by the student before the start of the educational process with the advice of an advisor. The basis for its development is a model curriculum, which includes mandatory subjects and elective subjects specified in the qualification requirements [1].

One of the main differences of the credit-module system is not only to provide students with the necessary educational documents, but also to provide the student with complete information about the higher education institution, areas, specialties, the organization of the educational process and knowledge control, preparation for independent study, rest and conditions for comprehensive development [4].

The introduction of the credit-module system of education based on the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) into the educational process in higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan significantly reduces the number of hours of study for students, as well as the professional quality requirements imposed on graduates by employers, and today the credit-module system, new educational standards, qualification requirements, curricula and subject programs are forcing us to look for new ways to organize training for graduates of the applied mathematics field. The introduction of this credit-module system into the educational process has dramatically accelerated the process of digitization.

In order to digitize the higher education management system in our republic, the Higher Education Management Information System (HEMIS) [5] was developed and put into practice within the Digital University project. This information system is responsible for automating the administrative, academic, scientific and financial activities of higher education institutions, organizing, monitoring and managing the educational process, providing distance online education services, and exchanging information with the ministerial information system. Today, work is underway to drastically reduce the number of various reports and information received from higher education institutions, abandon the paper form of their preparation, and digitize the management system. This system includes a module for managing administrative, educational, scientific and financial processes. By gradually introducing it in higher education institutions, the group journal, lesson schedule, exam schedule, student rating book, mastery records, attendance report, diploma and academic certificates were digitized in the educational process module. Also, in the administrative process module, maintaining information on the structure of the higher education institution, the number of students and their movements, the composition of the teaching staff, and preparing reports have been transferred to a digital system. We will present several ways to use the "HEMIS" information system in education in conditions of digitization.

For example, one of the most convenient digitalizations for students transferring or completing their studies is the practice of filling out a "circumvention sheet" ("обходной лист"). When graduating from educational institutions or transferring from one educational institution to another, the practice of filling out a circulation sheet is canceled and is carried out through the "HEMIS" information system.

In this case:

☞ the student will have the opportunity to send a request to receive an electronic circulation sheet through his profile;

☞ the accounting and personnel department, the dean's office of the faculty, the information resource center and the dormitory managers of the higher educational institution will form the student's electronic circulation sheet;

☞ the student will have the opportunity to familiarize himself with the circulation sheet formed and the comments included in it through his profile.

In conclusion, it can be said that with the introduction of digital technologies into the education system, the demand for increasing media

literacy is also increasing. The introduction of digital technologies into the educational process without the formation of media literacy will not provide high efficiency. This, in turn, will serve to organize authentic education and increase the effectiveness of education. It is precisely the organization of a modern digital education system that will help the future generation find its place in today's digital world. The proper organization of digital education serves as a sufficient basis for the development of the digital economy.

It is necessary to emphasize that with the development of digital technologies, it is necessary to develop media literacy in students in parallel in order to develop their skills in sorting daily information transmitted and received through information media, and to make the right decisions in any situation after receiving various information. It is as a result of the development of media literacy that students' skills in consciously analyzing and evaluating information have increased.

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